

A Study of Teachers's perspectives on cultural Diversity in Uttarakhand

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Abstract:

Uttarakhand has a culturally diverse culture separated into two main regions: Garhwal and Kumaon. This study aims to examine teachers' perspectives on cultural diversity in college. A quantitative and descriptive method using for this study. Simple Random sampling using for arranging data, Cultural intelligence scale standardized tool prepared by Kiranjit Kaur and Sesadeba Pany used to choose respondents. Population of this study is 40 teachers Garhwal and Kumaon. The findings of this survey revealed that respondents have knowledge and skills in other cultures. Teachers have a positive view of cultural diversity and its correlation and Instructor is a positive creator of multiculturalism. Cultural intelligence (CQ) is rapidly gaining prominence as a construct for predicting and explaining effectiveness and performance in cross-cultural situations, not only in the context of a multicultural workplace but also in other areas of life. Thus, valid and reliable Cultural intelligence (CQ) measurement is critical for Education business, society, and research.

Keywords: *Teacher's Perspective, Cultural Diversity, Cultural Intelligence, college, Multiculturalism.*

Introduction:

Cultural intelligence (CQ) is becoming increasingly popular. Globalization is the main factor behind this concentration. Guomundsdottir (2015: 175) argues that globalization has increased cross-cultural exchanges. Effective international leadership requires competence and sensitivity in intercultural dealings, as misunderstandings can have a significant impact on organizations (Earley, 2002). According to Thomas et al. (2008: 125), culturally competent behavior leads to improved intercultural communication. Cultural intelligence is essential for individuals and organizations to succeed in cross-cultural interactions. Efforts to apply CQ insights to commercial activities are hindered by the complex nature of the topic (Blasco, Feldt, & Jacobsen, 2012). Organizing knowledge is necessary. The authors acknowledge the work of

Ang, Van Dyne, and Rockstuhl (2015) and Bovornusvakool, Ardichvili, and Rana (2015) in reviewing the CQ literature. However, they believe that placing it within the concept and definition statement elements of the scientific knowledge framework (Babbie & Mouton, 2011) would add value. al. (2008: 125), culturally competent behavior leads to improved intercultural communication. Cultural intelligence is essential for individuals and organizations to succeed in cross-cultural interactions. Ang and Earley, on the other hand, discuss cognition from a social psychology viewpoint, which includes both culture-specific knowledge and metacognition, or understanding how cognition is rooted in a given cultural environment. Metacognition is defined as 'thinking about thinking' (Earley and Peterson, 2004: 105) as well as 'awareness of and control over one's thinking and learning activities' (Earley and Peterson, 2004; Thomas et al., 2008: 131). Early and Ang introduced the concept of cultural intelligence in their Stanford University press book published in 2003. Cultural intelligence refer to an individual's capability fo function effectively in situation characterized by cultural diversity (Ang& Dyne, 2008; Earley&Ang, 2003). Cultural intelligence was conceived at the turn of the 21 century,when the world was experiencing unprecedented globalization and interconnectedness multiculturalism is a uniformity of culture in the community. The term 'multiculturalism' refers to "the complex range of issues associated with cultural and religious diversity in a society, and the social management of the challenges and opportunities such diversity offers" (Nye, 2007 p. 110). The community includes interaction, tolerance and integration. In short, multiculturalism is a fact that must be accepted and understood positively to the development of culture. The cultural diversity of the community consists of people who are made up of diverse ethnic and cultural diversity but to live together. The life of their communities is not based on a single culture or a closed system but based on the values of the range.As the world becomes more globalized, cultural intelligence (CQ) has gained prominence in educational discourse. Although CQ is recognized as a valuable tool for flexibility and effective teaching in multicultural contexts (Karataş & Han, 2022; Wei et al., 2022), most research has focused on its implementation or lack thereof.

Multiculturalism:

The ideas of cultural pluralism that were articulated by Du Bois and Alain Locke gave rise multiculturalism to what is known as multiculturalism today. It dispels unfavorable stereotypes and promotes tolerance among various social groups. This is quite significant since, according

to the UN, culture plays a role in one-third of the world's main wars. People of various races, ethnicities, and nations coexisting in one society is a hallmark of multicultural societies. People preserve, transmit, celebrate, and share their distinct cultural ways of life, languages, artwork, customs, and behaviors in multicultural societies.

Cultural Diversity:

To grasp the union, let us first understand each of the two terms that make up cultural diversity: culture and variety. A society's beliefs, values, customs, and behavior are referred to as its culture. On the other hand, variety is the characteristic that distinguishes a class, including but not limited to color, language, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, or cultural background. The quality of multiculturalism, which is characterized as a set of values and beliefs that respects the existence of all diverse groups in society, recognizes and values their socio-cultural disparities, and encourages and facilitates their continued contribution within an inclusive cultural environment that welcomes everyone in the institution or society, is cultural diversity. Stated differently, it might be characterized as the existence of diverse cultural groups in a community. Incorporating individuals from a variety of backgrounds also entails embracing and promoting the skills, knowledge, and behaviors necessary to completely embrace, soothe, and support societal differences.

Review related Literature:

Intelligence regarding culture the ability to manage cultural diversity is a sign of cultural intelligence. According to Ang and Van Dyne (2008), those who are adept at managing cultural diversity possess cultural intelligence. It takes cultural intelligence to understand individual differences and self-adaptation to new cultural contexts (Deng and Gibson, 2008). Comprehending people from diverse cultural backgrounds is a necessary component of cultural intelligence. In order to collaborate with others, information gathering is also necessary. Culturally competent people, therefore, have a very high capacity for adaptation (Yeşil, 2009). There are four parts to cultural intelligence. (Ang et al., 2007) These characteristics are behavioral, motivational, cognitive, and Metacognitive intelligence. Furthermore, it highlights people's capacity to create mental processes (Van Dyne et al., 2010). Motivational intelligence is associated with the level of focus and enthusiasm people exhibit when adjusting to new cultural norms. Cultural norms, customs, and practices are reflected in cognitive intelligence. It comprises an understanding of various cultural social systems and values (İşçi et al., 2013).

Behavioral intelligence refers to the skill required to interact socially in a setting where different cultures coexist. Compatibility and adaptability are required for both verbal and nonverbal behavior types. Literature reviews can be done for a variety of reasons (Kable, Pich & Maslin-Prothero (2012). This includes the discovery of current and recognized theorizing on the subject, to discern the most widely accepted empirical observations in the study domain, to identify appropriate measures that have proved validity and reliability, and to evaluate established Definitions of essential terms relevant to the issue (Mouton, 2013). In conclusion, they frequently serve to frame the researcher's endeavors to frame the topic with greater knowledge Repository (De Vos et al., 2013). The growing interest in real word intelligence has identified new type of non-academic intelligence (Sternberg, 1997), that focused on specific content domains such as social intelligent (Thorndike & stein, 1937), emotional intelligent (Mayer and salovey. 1993) and practical Intelligence (Sternberg, 2000). Motivated by a practical reality globalization, CQ builds on some of this idea but with a focus on specific domain-intercultural setting (Earley & Ang, 2003). Just as emotional intelligence (EQ) complements cognitive intelligence (IQ) in predicting work effectiveness in interdependent domestic work context (Joseph & Newman, 2010, CQ is another important form of Intelligence that can increase our prediction of effectiveness in copy with diversity and functioning in new culture setting (Rockstuhl et al., 2011).

In the field of education, the idea of cultural intelligence (CQ) has drawn a lot of attention, especially when it comes to multicultural adaptability. The integration of design thinking and critical thinking in higher education was examined by Peng and Kueh (2022), who emphasized the significance of design thinking in navigating socially complicated contexts (Peng & Kueh, 2022). Similar to this, Mindshew et al. (2021) created a CQ framework especially for pharmacy education, emphasizing the importance of this framework in helping students become more culturally sensitive (Minshew et al., 2021).

Research objective:

- Identify the knowledge of teachers in college on cultural diversity.
- Identify the skill of teachers in implementation of cultural diversity.
- Examining theknowledge of teachers toward multiculturalism.

Research Methodology: The design of this study is quantitative and descriptive method involving 40 teachers of different region Kumaonregionand Garhwalregion. 20 teachers of

Kumaon region and 20 teachers of Garhwal region. Descriptive quantitative data in the form of the words spoken or written about human behavior that can be observed (2012 Jasmine). The researcher design will ensure that the information obtained is consistent with the Research questions to be observed, the information of obtained should use the most effective method (Konting 2005). This study attained our target with Cultural intelligence scale standardized and prepared by Kiranjit Kaur and Sesadeba Pany.

Sample:

Simple random sampling, according to Chua (2006), is a sampling process that selects responses from a set of individuals who share particular traits. As a result, some people in the study population were unable to participate as respondents. This is because the study focuses on the cultural diversity perspectives of Garhwal and Kumaon instructors. Twenty teachers from the Garhwal and twenty from Kumaon regions were chosen to serve as college administrators in the Champawat district. The researchers propose to evaluate certain relevant characteristics of teachers' knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and behaviors regarding cultural diversity through the selection of the sample for this study.

Table 1: Sample Distribution

Teachers	N	Percentage (%)
Garhwal Region	20	50%
Kumaon Region	20	50%

source: created by author

This study used a Cultural intelligence scale (CIS-KKPS) by Dr. Kiranjit Kaur and Dr. Sesadeba Pany. Cultural intelligence scale standardized and prepared by Kiranjit Kaur and Sesadeba Pany. This scale consists 22 items. It was administered on 388 foreign student studying different University of Punjab as group of 18+. This inventory is intended to measure cultural intelligence of eighteenth and above age group of college and university students, in four dimensions of cultural intelligence.

- Cognitive
- Metacognition
- Motivational
- Behavioral

Result and Discussion:

Table 2: Teacher’s view about cultural intelligence level

Levels	High count	High (%)	Average count	Average (%)	Low count	Low (%)	Total
Teachers	2	5.00%	31	77.50%	7	17.50%	40

source: created by author

According to the findings of this survey, 77.50 % of teachers understand and embrace cultural diversity, which is extremely useful in today's environment. This study results revealed that teachers had a positive mindset toward cultural variety, which is a cause of multiculturalism and cultural intelligence. The researcher found that the instructor is a favorable founder of multiculturalism. Teachers had an extensive understanding of cultural diversity, which is a very crucial pillar of cultural diversity. Through this study, the researcher discovered that teachers have made a significant contribution to cultural variety.

Suggestions to improve cultural intelligence:

Many organizations are investing in training and education in this area. But what can you, as an individual, do to improve your CQ? A smart place to start is to consider the attributes listed above and identify strategies to improve your talents in those areas. For example, you can improve your adaptability by stepping outside of your comfort zone and putting yourself in unfamiliar settings. Alternatively, you can develop empathy by frequently putting yourself in the shoes of others. Moving beyond those characteristics, here are some simple and practical strategies you may use to improve your cultural intelligence:

1. First and foremost, realize that no culture is superior to another. People, regardless of their cultural, religious, or political beliefs, largely want the same things: to live a decent life, do a good job, be happy, have a family (in whatever form that may take), have a safe roof over their heads, achieve some level of financial security, cultivate friendships and relationships, and so on. I'm not arguing that we ignore the various ways in which individuals differ; understanding our differences is vital, but we should also recognize that our own culture and experiences aren't inherently "better" than others. It's just different.
2. Consider the types of biases that may limit your vision. For example, how does your cultural background shape your worldview? Consider the prejudices that may exist within your organization.

3. Engage in stimulating interactions with people who have different experiences and ideas than your own.
4. Practice active listening. Becoming a better listener might help you grasp people's perspectives and expand your knowledge.
5. Consume content from throughout the world. I enjoy reading news stories and watching news programs from nations such as India and China because they help me learn how various cultures perceive the globe. You can also broaden your perspective by watching movies or reading books from various countries.
6. Watch a television show or read books or articles with alternative opinions. For example, if your views lean liberal, you might watch Fox News; it's unlikely to sway you from your political convictions (in fact, it may strengthen them even more!), but it will certainly help you understand what matters to individuals on the opposite end of the spectrum.
7. Attend a religious service for a different denomination than your own.
8. If feasible, immerse yourself in diverse cultures and ideas. If you visit a new country, for example, go to the food markets, take public transportation, and generally absorb the culture.

Research scope:

The study involve only 40 teachers of college at Champawat district in Uttarakhand, quantitative research sample selected simple random. This study is intended to examine the perspective of cultural diversity among teacher of various ethnic group in the college.

Conclusion:

This study contributes to our understanding of the predictors of global cultural intelligence effectiveness and how it varies across situations. The study highlights the significance of cultural intelligence (CQ) in predicting the effectiveness of multiculturalism in cross-border settings. Future study should focus on IQ, EQ, CQ, and other intelligences in predicting multicultural effectiveness in domestic and cross-cultural contexts. We also encourage additional research on situational elements that affect the linkages between different intelligences and the usefulness of cultural intelligence.

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